

Synthesis and characterization of hydroxido-bridged disc-shaped heptanuclear cobalt(II) coordination aggregate bearing six peripheral allyl units

Manisha Das, Dipmalya Basak and Debashis Ray*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, Kharagpur-721 302, West Bengal, India

E-mail: dray@chem.iitkgp.ac.in

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Dangling allyl functional group bearing Schiff base ligand of *o*-vanillin HL (2-((3-allylimino)methyl)-6-methoxyphenol) was used to compare its reactivity toward Co^{II} ions. From a single reaction in MeOH with Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O and NaOAc, the heptanuclear [Co^{II}₇(μ-L)₆(μ₃-OH)₆](ClO₄)₂·4H₂O (**1**) and mononuclear [CoL₂(OH)₂] (**2**) complexes were isolated as single crystals and powder solid respectively. The latter was in equilibrium with the former in the solutions as identified by mass spectral analysis. X-Ray structural characterization of **1** revealed a planar disc-like [Co₇L₆] compound formed from coordination self-assembly. Complex **1** matures around a central Co^{II} ion bordered by a regular {Co^{II}₆} hexagon bound to six hydroxide groups and six L⁻ units. The dicationic species hold a wheel-shaped structure encompassing a central Co^{II} ion, linked to six other peripheral Co^{II} ions by the O atoms provided by six μ₃-OH bridges. Mass spectroscopic evidences suggest a stepwise assembly process for the formation of a Co₇ species from the reaction of [Co(H₂O)₆](ClO₄)₂ with a O,O,N donor ligand.

Keywords: Co^{II} aggregates, self-assembly, Schiff base, allyl imine, disc complex.

Introduction

Design and gram scale synthesis of cobalt ion based aggregate complexes purely depend on the selection of newer ligand systems. In recent years this family of metal ion complexes have been widely studied due to their attractive structures¹, distinctive magnetic behaviors² and catalytic functions³. In the area of cobalt ion catalyzed organic reactions and transformations in presence of symmetrical binucleating ligands, the actual catalytic species responsible for the conversions are not known with certainty⁴. Choice of metal ion as cobalt for these reactions are guided by its low cost and toxicity in contrast to other 3d ions. The contemporary interest in cobalt ion bearing coordination complexes has further been intensified with the development of several important reactions like cyclopropanation of alkenes, cycloadditions, reductive couplings, addition reactions, carbocyclizations, cross-couplings, enyne couplings, and C-H activation reactions^{5a}. Allyl amine has been shown to be a reactive substrate while showing thiol-ene 'click' reactions using ultrasound in both toluene and water in the presence of air^{5b}. The method is particularly effective in aqueous solutions in the presence of Schiff base C=N function and alkene moiety within the ligand frame to give the opportunity to study cata-

lytic reactions on these functional groups through activation due to coordination from single or multiple cobalt ions. To obtain either the mononuclear species or the multinuclear aggregate, a diversity of ligand types and a variety of trials for synthetic methodologies have to be followed and standardized. In this context, the role of ligand design and alteration of reaction conditions with respect to the added base for *in situ* generation of auxiliary bridges and metal ion salts are essential in directing the different reaction paths. In recent year, the heptanuclear mixed valent cobalt cluster [Co^{II}₅Co^{III}₂(mdea)₄(N₃)₂(CH₃CN)₆(OH)₂(H₂O)₂·4ClO₄] (H₂mdea = N-methyldiethanolamine) has shown remarkable water oxidation activity under visible light irradiation condition while evaluating its catalytic potency⁶. Both symmetric and asymmetric phenol-based ligand systems (HL) with two adjacent coordinating units are suitable for the generation of {ML} and {M₂L} species in solution. In presence of solvent derived or metal ion salt derived auxiliary bridges the {ML} and {M₂L} units can initiate and regulate the formation, growth and stabilization of high nuclearity complexes⁷. In solution the most readily available auxiliary bridges of this type are hydroxido (HO⁻) ions. Similar to that observed in biomineralizations and polyoxometallate formation, these ions are

branded to bridge 2 to 3 metal ions in controlling the nuclearity and topology of the coordination aggregates⁸. This water derived HO⁻ groups can connect 2 to 3 metal ions in $\mu_{1,1}$ and $\mu_{1,1,1}$ modes (Scheme 1). Availability of HO⁻ ions in sufficient number in the reaction medium modifies the coordination mode of the parent ligand to influence the result of the attempted metal-ion-ligand reactions. In trying to find out the reactivity patterns of MeO-substituted phenol-based ligand system for its simple coordinating ability versus coordination aggregate formation in presence of available metal ion clips we have been interested in exploring the coordination and crystallization behavior of previously unknown (2-((3-allylimino)methyl)-6-methoxyphenol) (HL; Chart 1) ligand with Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O. The presence of allylimine arm of the ligand is expected to show catalytic transformation such as thiolene reaction useful for dendrimer synthesis and surface patterning⁹. The asymmetric coordinating nature of HL, with respect to the phenolate ion, is expected to favor the assembly of angularly disposed dinuclear or trinuclear moieties having several vacant coordination sites.

Herein we report the standardized reaction methods and crystal structure of the heptanuclear [Co^{II}₇(μ -L)₆(μ_3 -OH)₆](ClO₄)₂·2CH₃CN·2H₂O (**1**), growing on six HO⁻ bridges entrapping the central Co^{II} ion and linking it to six peripheral Co^{II} centers to develop a disc-shaped structure. After growing the single crystals for **1**, the supersaturated mother liquor provided us with the mononuclear complex [Co(μ -L)₂(OH₂)₂] (**2**). In the former case the binding modes of L⁻ and HO⁻ are different from L⁻ and H₂O in latter (Scheme 1).

Chart 1. Ligand HL.

Scheme 1. Binding modes of L⁻ and HO⁻ in **1**.

Experimental

Reagents and materials:

The chemicals used were obtained from the following sources: Cobalt(II) carbonate, sodium acetate, sodium hydroxide from SD Fine-chem Limited, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde from Spectrochem (India) and allyl amine (98+%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar (India). Hydrated cobalt(II) perchlorate was freshly prepared by treating hydrated cobalt(II) carbonate with 1:1 aqueous solution of perchloric acid followed by evaporation of excess water on steam bath. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade materials and used as received without further purification. All manipulations were performed under standard wet laboratory conditions in presence of air.

Synthesis:

Ligand HL [2-((allylimino)methyl)-6-methoxy-phenol]:

To a MeOH solution of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.152 g, 1 mmol), allyl amine (0.10 g, 1 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) was added with constant stirring and then refluxed for 2 h. Complete evaporation of the solvent in air over 12 h gave an orange oily substance, which was dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. The oily substance was characterized by FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy and used directly for reactions with metal ion salts without further purification. FTIR (cm⁻¹, KBr disk): 1636 (m); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ppm): 8.30–8.53 (1H, s, imine H), 7.26–7.65 (1H, Ar-H), 5.97–6.06 (1H, vinyl H), 5.13–5.23 (2H, vinyl H), 4.22–4.23 (2H, d, allyl H), 2.27 (3H, s, methyl H); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, ppm): 165.04 (imine C), 124.06–163.36 (Ar C), 116.62–127.54 (alkene C), 53.93 (secondary C attached to imine N), 20.32–20.35 (methyl C).

Complexes:

To a stirring solution of Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.365 g, 1 mmol) in MeOH, solid NaOAc (0.082 g, 1 mmol) was added slowly to get a light pink solution. After 15 min of stirring, the as prepared HL (approx. 0.19 g, 1 mmol) in MeOH (10 mL) was added to it resulting in a brown solution which darkened following addition of NaOH (0.040 g, 1 mmol) solution. The stirring of the entire reaction mixture was continued for 2 h. The solution was then filtered and kept in air at room temperature for slow evaporation and crystallization.

[Co^{II}₇(μ -L)₆(μ_3 -OH)₆](ClO₄)₂·2CH₃CN·2H₂O (**1**): Some crystalline material appeared at the bottom of the conical

after 2 days. The mother solution was decanted in another conical and the residual crystalline material was dissolved in MeCN. Brown needle shaped single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction was obtained from the MeCN solution after 4 days. Yield ~30%. Microanalytical data are consistent with the formula $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}_7(\mu\text{-L})_6(\mu_3\text{-OH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{70}\text{H}_{88}\text{Co}_7\text{N}_8\text{O}_{28}\text{Cl}_2$ (1972.86 g mol⁻¹): C, 42.61; H, 4.50; N, 5.68. Found: C, 42.62; H, 4.50; N, 5.67; Selected FTIR bands: (KBr, cm⁻¹, vs = very strong, br = broad, s = strong, m = medium): 3418 (br), 1617 (vs), 1089 (vs), 619 (m); UV-Vis spectra [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹): (MeCN solution) 682 (48), 558 (200), 521 (178), 491 (183), 357 (24345), 266 (56845), 233 (113522). Δ_{M} (Molar conductivity): (MeCN solution) 310 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹.

$[\text{Co}(\mu\text{-L})_2(\text{OH})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (**2**): From the decanted left over solution brown crystalline material was obtained after 2 days. Yield ~35%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{CoN}_2\text{O}_{10}\text{Cl}$ (574.85 g mol⁻¹): C, 45.97; H, 4.91; N, 4.87. Found: C, 46.05; H, 4.98; N, 4.90; Selected FTIR bands: (KBr, cm⁻¹, vs = very strong, br = broad, s = strong, m = medium): 3418 (br), 1624 (vs), 1100 (vs), 1078 (vs), 624 (m), 604 (m); UV-Vis spectra [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹): (MeCN solution) 679 (212), 604 (293), 398 (6531), 258 (57596), 237 (46648). Δ_{M} (Molar conductivity): (MeCN solution) 145 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹.

Physical measurements:

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) of the compounds were performed with a Perkin-Elmer model 240C elemental analyzer. A Shimadzu UV 3100 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer and a Perkin-Elmer RX1 spectrometer were used to record the solution electronic absorption spectra and FTIR spectra respectively. Mass spectra were recorded on an Agilent 1260/6120 LC/MS system fitted with a single quadrupole mass analyzer.

Crystal data collection and refinement:

Appropriate single crystal of **1** was chosen for data collection on a Bruker SMART APEX-II CCD X-ray diffractometer furnished with a graphite-monochromated Mo K α (λ = 0.71073 Å) radiation by the ω scan (width of 0.3° frame⁻¹) method at 293 K with a scan rate of 5 s per frame. SAINT and XPREP softwares¹⁰ were used for data processing and space group determination. Direct method technique from SHELXS-2014¹¹ were used for structure determination and then refined by full-matrix least squares technique using SHELXL (2014/7)¹² program package within WINGX version

1.80.05¹³. Data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects; an empirical absorption correction was applied using the SADABS¹⁴. The locations of the heaviest atoms (Co) were determined easily, and the O, N and C atoms were subsequently determined from the difference Fourier maps. These atoms are refined anisotropically. The H atoms were incorporated at calculated positions and refined with fixed geometry and riding thermal parameters with respect to their carrier atoms. Crystallographic diagrams were presented using DIAMOND software¹⁵. A summary of the crystal data and relevant refinement parameters is given in Table 1. Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as supplementary publications CCDC-1850235. This data can also be obtained free of cost at www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html (or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre).

Table 1. Crystal parameters and refinement data of complex **1**

Parameters	1
Formula	$\text{C}_{70}\text{H}_{88}\text{Cl}_2\text{Co}_7\text{N}_8\text{O}_{28}$
F.W. (g mol ⁻¹)	1972.86
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
Crystal color	Red
Crystal size(mm ³)	0.35×0.27×0.20
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.7098(10)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.6821(14)
<i>c</i> (Å)	25.625(2)
α (deg)	90.00
β (deg)	90.241(3)
γ (deg)	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	4029.4(7)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D_c</i> (g cm ⁻³)	1.623
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.556
<i>F</i> (000)	2014
<i>T</i> (K)	293
Total reflns.	45912
<i>R</i> (int)	0.0415
Unique reflns.	6947
Observed reflns.	6086
Parameters	537
<i>R</i> ₁ ; <i>wR</i> ₂ (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.0443, 0.1220
GOF (<i>F</i> ²)	1.104
Largest diff peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	1.662, -0.838
CCDC No.	1850235

Results and discussion

Synthesis: HL was obtained from a single step condensation reaction between two components 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and allyl amine in 1:1 molar ratio in MeOH after 2 h reflux. Reactivity of HL with $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was next assessed in presence of both NaOAc and NaOH as combined bases in 1:1:1 molar ratios. Variations of molar ratios did not yield any other product from the attempted reactions. The reaction provided a deep brown solution after the addition of NaOH solution. Upon slow evaporation of solution in air after 2 days a brown colored crystalline material was obtained. Recrystallization of this solid from MeCN solution provided brown needle shaped single crystals of **1** suitable for X-ray diffraction analysis after 7 days in 48% yield [eq. (1)] (Scheme 2).

Interestingly after isolation of **1** the mother solution on

standing in air for next 2 days yielded a brown crystalline oxidized compound. This was identified as $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (**2**) from elemental analysis, conductance measurements, UV-Vis measurements and FT-IR analysis. For the generation of **2** a different molar ratio of 2:1:1 for HL, $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaOH was utilized for the reaction presented by [eq. (2)] (Scheme 2).

Following separation of **1**, the isolation of **2** clearly indicated the availability of different cobalt ion based species including $\{\text{CoL}_2\}$ type following oxidation of the metal ion center. Availability of bare $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}_{\text{aq}}$ species in solution led to its incorporation in **1**. Mass spectroscopic analysis indicated the presence of several fragments till we reach to the Co_7 unit as well as the fragments present in equilibrium. Since the reaction is performed with 1:1 metal ion to ligand molar ratio and the formation of **1** demand seven Co^{II} ions per six ligand molecules, the concentration of metal ions in solution de-

Scheme 2. Initial separation of **1** and separation of oxidized product **2** at the end.

creases after **1** is formed resulting in **2**. Initial formation of {CoL} fragments under higher Co^{II} ion concentration is thus expected.

Spectral characterizations:

FTIR spectra: The characteristic spectrum of HL, **1** and **2** in the powder as synthesized form are depicted in Fig. 1. HL exhibits a sharp band at 1628 cm⁻¹ due to stretching of the imine bond ($\bar{\nu}_{C=N}$). A shoulder at 1645 cm⁻¹ appears as a result of C=C stretching ($\bar{\nu}_{C=C}$) of the allyl group. In **1** the band due to C=N stretch ($\bar{\nu}_{C=N}$) is shifted to lower frequency upon coordination to Co^{II} ion and appears at 1617 cm⁻¹. The presence of perchlorate anion is discernable from the bands at 1089 cm⁻¹ and 619 cm⁻¹ due to $\bar{\nu}_{Cl-O}$ stretching and δ_{O-Cl-O} bending modes of vibrations respectively. A broad band at 3418 cm⁻¹ is due to $\bar{\nu}_{OH}$ of the bridging hydroxido groups and lattice water molecules. The band due to -C=N stretch appears at 1624 cm⁻¹ for **2**. Two bands at 1100 and

1078 cm⁻¹ arise as a result of $\bar{\nu}_{Cl-O}$ stretch of the perchlorate counter anion. Bands due to δ_{O-Cl-O} bending appear at 624 and 604 cm⁻¹. The broad band at 3418 cm⁻¹ is due to $\bar{\nu}_{OH}$ of the coordinated water molecules.

Electronic spectra: Stability in organic solution medium and their distinctive features of **1** and **2** were measured in MeCN within 200–800 nm (Fig. 2). For **1**, position and intensity of the bands at 682 nm ($\epsilon = 48 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 558 nm ($\epsilon = 200 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 521 nm ($\epsilon = 178 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 291 nm ($\epsilon = 183 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were typical for d-d transitions for anionic ligand bound Co^{II} ions in two types of distorted octahedral coordination geometry. The lowest energy band at 682 nm can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions while the bands at 558 nm and 291 nm arise due to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. The band at 521 nm has its origin due to spin-orbit interactions. The PhO⁻ → Co^{II} LMCT band appeared at 357 nm ($\epsilon = 24345 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$

Fig. 1. Visually distinguishable spectra of HL, **1** and **2**.

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of **1** (Left) and **2** (Right) in MeCN.

cm^{-1}). Still higher energy bands at 266 nm ($\epsilon = 56845 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 233 nm ($\epsilon = 113522 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ LLCT bands respectively, originating from allylic and aromatic C=C and imine C=N bonds of the ligand backbone.

In case of **2** the corresponding d-d transitions were detected at 679 nm ($\epsilon = 212 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 604 nm ($\epsilon = 293 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting presence of Co^{III} ion. The band at 679 nm is due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ transitions while the band at 604 nm can be attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. The $\text{PhO}^- \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ LMCT occurred at 398 nm ($\epsilon = 6531 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The high energy bands at 258 nm ($\epsilon = 57596 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 237 nm ($\epsilon = 46648 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is due to intraligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ LLCT bands respectively.

Descriptions of crystal structures:

$[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}_7(\mu\text{-L})_6(\mu_3\text{-OH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CN} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**): The structure features a heptanuclear cationic coordination aggregate $[\text{Co}_7(\mu\text{-L})_6(\mu_3\text{-OH})_6]^{2+}$ capped and stabilized by six L^- in bridging mode. The presence of two perchlorate counter anions neutralizes two positive charges on the cationic part and provided a disc-like structure as shown in Fig. 3. Six solvent derived HO^- groups in μ_3 bridging mode surround the central Co^{II} center and supplement interconnections between all the seven cobalt centers. The complex crystallizes in monoclinic $\text{P}2_1/c$ space group with $Z = 2$ and selected metric parameters are summarized in Table 1. The formation of the $[\text{Co}_7]$ aggregate was initiated by the self-assembly of six $\{\text{CoL}\}$ fragments around a central $\text{Co}^{2+}_{\text{aq}}$ or $\{\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\}^{2+}$ species. For the latter type use of NaOH base allowed deprotonation of the Co^{II} bound water molecules. The formation of heptametallic molecular disc took place from the coordination of six L^- in $\mu\text{-}\eta_1:\eta_2:\eta_1$ mode supplemented by six bridging HO^- groups in μ_3 mode. Alternatively, the structure can be visualized as six fused cubanes of missing corners and sharing two adjacent faces (Fig. 3). The average diameter of the $[\text{Co}_7]$ disc thus formed is 6.253 Å (6.263(2) Å for $\text{Co}4 \cdots \text{Co}4$; 6.269(9) Å for $\text{Co}2 \cdots \text{Co}2$; 6.226(1) Å for $\text{Co}3 \cdots \text{Co}3$), which is double the average length of the adjacent $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} \cdots \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ separations of 3.126 Å (3.131(6) Å for $\text{Co}1 \cdots \text{Co}4$; 3.134(9) Å for $\text{Co}1 \cdots \text{Co}2$; 3.113(0) Å for $\text{Co}1 \cdots \text{Co}3$). The connectivity established by the $\mu_3\text{-OH}^-$ groups is unsymmetrical providing three different Co-O bonds (2.032(3), 2.114(3) and 2.168(3) Å for O7; 2.027(3), 2.101(2)

and 2.158(3) Å for O8; 2.019(3), 2.093(3) and 2.163(3) Å for O9). The central Co1 ion stays in a more symmetric O6 environment of intermediate Co-O separations of 2.114(3), 2.101(2) and 2.094(3) Å and O-Co1-O *cis*-angles span a range within 82.21(10)–97.79(10)°. All peripheral Co2, Co3 and Co4 ions on the other hand were within distorted octahedral O5N donor set and O-Co-O *cis*-angles cover a wide range of 77.83(10)–113.96(11)° for Co2, 71.54(10)–115.19(11)° for Co3 and 77.14(10)–115.59(11)° for Co4. The smaller angle is due to the coordination from OMe group *cis* to the phenoxido O atom. Strained coordination of OMe group provides a stressed five member chelate ring and longer Co-O bonds of 2.307(3), 2.349(3) and 2.418(2) Å. The phenoxido bridge angles (Co-OPh-Co) around PhO^- groups are 103.11(12)°, 103.28(11)° and 103.44(11)°. These angles are smaller than trigonal planar and tetrahedral angles and greater than regular cubane angle (~90°). Interestingly the hydroxido-bridge angles (Co-OH-Co) around HO^- clips are within 93.26(10)–99.47(11)° ranges, providing hexacubane arrangement around the Co7 disc wherein the individual cubes are defective and distorted in terms of bridge angles around PhO^- and HO^- groups. The Co-N separations are 2.084(4) Å for Co2-N3, 2.086(3) Å for Co3-N1 and 2.089(3) Å for Co4-N2. The Co-OPh distances cover a range from 1.999(3) to 2.072(3) Å, compared to the Co-OH distances at much wider range from 2.019(3)–2.168(3) Å. Both of these distances are shorter than the strained Co-OMe distances within 2.307(3)–2.418(2) Å. The bond valence sum (BVS) values^{16,17} for Co1, Co2, Co3 and Co4 centers within the Co_7 unit clearly indicate +2 states for all. The BVS values are 1.978 for Co1, 1.960 for Co2, 1.982 for Co3 and 1.957 for Co4. Mixed solvent (H_2O and MeCN) of crystallization, two molecules each, is found in the crystalline framework of the Co_7 coordination aggregate. During crystallization one of the water molecule O1W is trapped in the lattice through hydrogen bond interaction with H8 of bridging hydroxide oxygen O8 ($\text{O1W} \cdots \text{H8}(\text{O8}), 1.943(6) \text{ \AA}$). Use of *o*-vanillin only, could not provide the equivalent Co_7 complex having oxygen environments. Use of Schiff base on the other hand provided imine group needed for the six Co-N bonds at the periphery and formation of cyclic ring structure. The pendant allyl functions attached to the imine functions provided six localized π -electron cloud and hydrophobic shield for the coordination aggregate to grow from solution.

Fig. 3. (a) Molecular structure of **1**. H atoms and perchlorate ions omitted for clarity. (b) Core view of Co₇ disc with important bond distances. Colour code: Co, purple; O, red; N, blue; C, grey.

Comparison of the present structure with our previously reported Co₇ disc¹⁸ structure shows that the hexagon formed by the peripheral metal ions in the present case is unsymmetrical in nature as opposed to highly symmetrical disposition in the previous case. Another Co₇ complex of different topology, unlike our type, showed that the core is made of only two μ_3 HO⁻ bridges and protected by terminal H₂O, CH₃CN groups and capping by N-methyldiethanolamine ligand at the periphery showing water oxidation activity^{6a}. The complex [Co₇(ampd)₆(SCN)₆]⁻ (ampdH₂ = 2-amino-2-methyl-1,3-propanediol), consists of seven coplanar cobalt ions which is bound to six ampd²⁻ ligands and six terminal NCS⁻ groups and shows solvent dependent catecholase activity¹⁹. In an coordination environment consisting of greater number of N donor atoms, complex [Co₇(bzp)₆(N₃)₈(CH₃O)₄].2ClO₄.2H₂O (bzp = 2-benzoyl pyridine) was obtained with two purely μ_3 -azido bridged sites²⁰.

ESI-Mass spectroscopy. Mass spectrometry has been effectively utilized in the present study to identify the number of metal ions and solution stability of the high-nuclearity aggre-

gate. It allowed identification of the building blocks during the assembly processes. To identify the various fragments present in solution, ESI mass spectra of **1** in MeCN was scrutinized (Fig. 4). The spectra exhibited a moderately intense peak at $m/z = 836.4$ due to the presence of dicationic heptanuclear species $\{[Co_7(\mu-L)_6(\mu_3-OH)_6](H_2O)\}^{2+}$ (C₇₀H₈₈Cl₂Co₇N₈O₂₈; Calcd. 836.5). A high intensity peak at $m/z = 842.0$ can be assigned to the trinuclear species $\{Co_3(\mu-L)_2L(H_2O)_3(CH_3CN)\}^+$ (C₃₅H₄₅Co₃N₄O₉; Calcd. 842.1). Another trinuclear species was identified at $m/z = 822.6$ $\{Co_3(\mu-L)_2L(\mu-OH)_2(CH_3CN)\}^+$ (C₃₅H₄₁Co₃N₄O₈; Calcd. 822.1). A peak at $m/z = 439.4$ can be assigned to the mononuclear species $\{CoL_2\}$ (C₂₂H₂₄CoN₂O₄; Calcd. 439.1). The base peak at $m/z = 192.4$ arise from the free ligand (H₂L⁺) in protonated form (C₁₁H₁₄NO₄; Calcd. 192.1). The spectra for **2** in MeCN (Fig. 5) displayed a base peak at $m/z = 439.4$ due to the presence of the molecular species $\{CoL_2\}$ (C₂₂H₂₄CoN₂O₄; Calcd. 439.1). This also confirms the formation of *bis*-chelate at higher concentration of ligand anion following the separation of [Co₇] complex. A low intensity peak

Table 2. Selected bond distances and angles for **1**

Bond lengths (Å)					
Complex 1					
Co1-O7	2.114(3)	Co3-O3	2.072(3)	Co4-O20	2.418(2)
Co1-O8	2.101(2)	Co3-O5	2.307(3)	Co1-Co2	3.134(9)
Co1-O9	2.094(3)	Co3-O7	2.168(3)	Co1-Co3	3.113(0)
Co2-O1	2.061(3)	Co3-O9	2.019(3)	Co1-Co4	3.131(6)
Co2-O2	2.349(3)	Co3-N1	2.086(3)	Co2-Co4	3.169(9)
Co2-O6	2.004(3)	Co4-O3	1.995(3)	Co3-Co4	3.193(0)
Co2-O7	2.032(3)	Co4-O6	2.044(3)	Co2-Co2	6.269(9)
Co2-O8	2.159(3)	Co4-O8	2.027(3)	Co3-Co3	6.226(1)
Co2-N3	2.084(4)	Co4-O9	2.163(3)	Co4-Co4	6.263(2)
Co3-O1	1.999(3)	Co4-N2	2.089(3)		
Bond angles (°)					
Complex 1					
O8-Co1-O7	97.79(10)	O8-Co2-O2	99.66(10)	O6-Co4-N2	105.93(12)
O8-Co1-O7	82.21(10)	N3-Co2-O2	81.81(12)	O8-Co4-O6	80.02(11)
O9-Co1-O7	97.19(10)	O1-Co3-O5	93.93(11)	O8-Co4-O9	82.27(10)
O9-Co1-O7	82.81(10)	O1-Co3-O7	77.72(10)	O8-Co4-N2	100.46(12)
O9-Co1-O8	97.75(10)	O1-Co3-O9	115.19(11)	Co3-O1-Co2	103.28(11)
O9-Co1-O8	82.26(10)	O1-Co3-N1	87.87(12)	Co2-O6-Co4	103.11(12)
O9-Co1-O8	82.25(10)	O3-Co3-O5	71.54(10)	Co4-O3-Co3	103.44(11)
O9-Co1-O8	97.74(10)	O3-Co3-O7	91.12(10)	Co1-O7-Co3	93.26(10)
O1-Co2-O8	89.44(10)	O3-Co3-N1	104.27(12)	Co2-O7-Co1	98.21(11)
O1-Co2-N3	104.17(13)	O7-Co3-O5	98.22(10)	Co2-O7-Co3	98.53(11)
O6-Co2-O2	95.12(11)	O9-Co3-O3	78.78(10)	Co1-O8-Co2	94.77(10)
O6-Co2-O7	113.96(11)	O9-Co3-O7	83.23(10)	Co4-O8-Co1	98.67(10)
O6-Co2-O8	77.83(10)	O9-Co3-N1	98.14(12)	Co4-O8-Co2	98.40(11)
O6-Co2-N3	88.13(12)	N1-Co3-O5	88.23(12)	Co1-O9-Co4	94.71(10)
O7-Co2-O1	79.51(10)	O3-Co4-O8	115.59(11)	Co3-O9-Co1	98.38(11)
O7-Co2-O2	150.53(11)	O3-Co4-O9	77.14(10)	Co3-O9-Co4	99.47(11)
O7-Co2-O8	82.73(10)	O3-Co4-N2	87.91(12)		
O7-Co2-N3	102.94(12)	O6-Co4-O9	89.69(11)		

at $m/z = 192.4$ is due to the protonated ligand H_2L^+ ($C_{11}H_{14}NO_4$; Calcd. 192.1).

Proposed aggregation pathway: Taking clues from the presence of various fragments in solution from ESI-MS spectra, a plausible route for molecular aggregation for Co_7 disc formation can be indicated. The strategic course of reaction involving addition of chosen metal ion salt to as synthesized HL, in MeOH solution in presence of NaOH provided complex **1**. Lesser solubility of the Co_7 molecular aggregate in the reaction medium is also another reason for the separation of coordination aggregate in crystalline form. In solution complex **1** was present in equilibrium with the $\{CoL_2\}^+$ spe-

cies as detected while recording the mass spectra of **1**. Also in the same mixture the trinuclear fragments $\{Co_3(\mu-L)_2L(H_2O)_3(CH_3CN)\}^+$ and $\{Co_3(\mu-L)_2L(\mu-OH)_2(CH_3CN)\}^+$, the precursors for Co_7 were present. Trapping of Co^{2+}_{aq} or $\{Co(H_2O)_6\}^{2+}$ species by these fragments was responsible for the construction and self-assembly of molecular aggregate providing complex **1**. Due to its lower solubility, the Co_7 complex crystallizes out of the solution medium shifting the equilibrium to the right. As the aggregation progresses the reaction medium was further depleted of Co^{II} ions which in turn favors the formation of **2**.

Fig. 4. ESI-MS spectra of 1 in MeCN.

Fig. 5. ESI-MS spectra of 2 in MeCN.

Scheme 3. Schematic course of aggregation for the generation of **1**.

Conclusions

Unique coordination ability of a $\text{MeO}^{\ominus}\text{O}^{\ominus}\text{N}$ donor ligand having dangling allyl arm at the imine end has been utilized for the stepwise growth of the heptanuclear disk-shaped coordination aggregate **1**. Self-sorting of metal ion-ligand anion based coordination fragments in two different molar ratios and the course of aggregation for a Co_7 complex has been demonstrated utilizing strategies based on *in situ* generated bridging groups under a chosen reaction condition. The most important $\{\text{CoO}_6\}$ core connectivity was established by the use of six $\mu_3\text{-OH}^-$ groups giving three different types of Co-O bonds. For a self-assembly category of reaction, each L^- was forced for $\mu\text{-}\eta_1\text{:}\eta_2\text{:}\eta_1$ type coordination to six Co^{II} centers augmented by six water derived HO^- groups bridging in μ_3 mode. Compound **1** is a new member within the infrequent family of heptametallichexacubanes in the family of coordination aggregates. Nitrogen coordination through

imine function gave six Co-N bonds and the cyclic ring structure around the central cobalt ion. The pendant allyl functions provided localized π -electron cloud from six such units and hydrophobic protecting environment for the growth of the coordination aggregate during crystallization. Mass spectral evidences were in support of the room temperature *step-by-step assembly process*, when the reaction was performed in the presence of NaOH. Two key trinuclear reaction intermediates were observed along with the mononuclear species forming at the end of the whole reaction path.

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Supporting information

Crystallographic data of the complexes have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center with the CCDC numbers 1850235. This data can also be obtained free of cost at www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html (or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre).

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